

NUMERICAL MODELS WITH LAYERED ELEMENTS FOR NOMEX HONEYCOMB CORE UNDER FLATWISE COMPRESSION

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Keywords: Composite plates, Modal analysis, Identification, Properties, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

Nomex honeycomb core is weak in out-of-plane direction and it is necessary to evaluate its collapse behavior prior to its high-efficient usage. To this end, five different modelling methods of the Nomex honeycomb sandwich structures under flatwise compression were proposed and developed based on the structural features of the Nomex honeycomb cell walls. The simulation results were compared with the test results and possible usage of each method was also discussed. The unit-cell models with shell elements representing the layered cell wall are valid to be used for compression simulation. The whole-scale model with shell elements representing the layered cell wall can be used to simulate the crushing process and more general loading cases, such as impact. The unit cell model with solid elements and cohesive elements can be used to investigate the debonding fracture of the double cell.

1 INTRODUCTION

NomexTM honeycomb core is normally manufactured from phenolic resin-impregnated aramid paper in an expansion process, which begins with printing adhesive lines on the sheets of Nomex aramid fibre paper, then stacks the sheets with a shift and expanse the cells into hexagon shape, and finally dips into resin and finally cure to desired density [1]. Sandwich structures with Nomex honeycomb cores are extensively used in aerospace industries. Examples of the application of Nomex honeycomb cored sandwich in airplane are floors, doors, wing flaps, wing-body fairings, rudders, overhead stowage bins, ceiling or sidewall panels, engine cowls, spoilers, nacelles, and radomes, etc [2-3]. However, the honeycomb cores are prone to collapse at rather low transvers load and displacement values due to their comparatively low mechanical properties in out-of-plane direction, which is an obstacle to their extensively use in primary loading aerospace structures in the future[4-5]. Hence, the evaluation of the collapse behaviour of the core is very important for its application.

Consequently, some efforts have been applied to study the response of the honeycomb sandwich structures subjected to transverse loadings. Generally, the research methods include experimental, analytical, numerical methods. However, the experimental method is rather costly and time consuming. The analytical equations are difficult to solve the complicated problems where failure is related. Therefore, many researches propose some numerical methods, and based on the modelling method of the honeycomb core, these methods can be generally divided into three groups: 1) the multi-cellular core is usually modelled as equivalent spring elements [6]; 2) equivalent three-dimensional continuum elements [7-9]; 3) explicit two-dimensional shell elements [10-13]. These methods, more or less, need

tests for each type of cores with different parameters, such as height, cell size, wall thickness, resin ratio (relating to the core density), etc. Furthermore, they cannot be used to investigate the failure mechanism.

Virtual testing using finite element simulations is an efficient way to investigate the mechanical behaviour of small- and large-scale structures reducing time- and cost-expensive prototype tests. Furthermore, numerical models allow for efficient parameter studies or optimisations. Once the mechanical behaviour has been correctly identified and modelled, Virtual testing method can be applied to simulate the more general load cases, such as impact and bending tests. Thus, decrease the test costs [14]. Based on the virtual testing methods, finite element models of the honeycomb core subjected to transverse loading were developed in this study. The advantages and applications of them are also evaluated.

2 GEOMETRY FEATURES AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

A typical Nomex honeycomb core with 50 mm in length, 50 mm in width and 20 mm in height is shown in Fig. 1. The core consists of regular hexagonal Nomex honeycombs with cell size and density of the honeycomb core being 3.2 mm and 48 kg/m^3 , respectively. The honeycombs were manufactured in an expansion process from Nomex Type 412 aramid paper with nominal thickness of 0.05 mm and an areal density of 40 g/m^2 . The three material directions of the honeycomb core are illustrated in Fig. 1(b), referred as the L-direction (ribbon direction), W-direction (direction perpendicular to the ribbon), and the out-of-plane direction as the T-direction (through-the-thickness direction). The cell walls oriented in the L-direction are twice as thick (double cell walls) as the other cell walls (single cell walls), which is a result of gluing the paper sheets in the manufacturing process [1,15].

Fig.1 Appearances and geometries Nomex honeycomb core (dimensions in mm)

Both the single and double cell walls are layered structure. The single cell walls consist of two resin layers and an aramid paper layer, with each resin layer of 0.008 mm thick and paper layer of 0.054 mm thick. The aramid paper layer is understandably placed between the two resin layers. The double cell walls consist of two resin layers and two aramid paper layers. The two aramid paper layers are glue together. The thickness of the resin layer and paper layer in the double cell walls are the same with those in the single cell walls. Therefore, the total thickness of the resin-dipped honeycomb single cell walls is 0.07 mm, and that of double cell walls is 0.124 mm. The mechanical and physical properties of the aramid paper and Phenolic resin used in the Nomex honeycomb core are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical and physical properties of the aramid paper and phenolic resin [16]

	E_{MD} (GPa)	E_{XD} (GPa)	S_{MD} (MPa)	S_{XD} (MPa)	δ_{MD} (%)	δ_{XD} (%)	μ (-)	ρ (kg/m^3)
Paper	3.1	1.6	88	35	9.6	6.5	0.3	740
Resin	5.8		60		.01		0.389	1380

3 NUMERICAL MODELS

Five different models were developed to investigate different aspects of honeycomb core under compression. Four of them are unit cell models and the other one is whole scale model. The regions covered by different unit cells are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2 Unit cells of the honeycomb core

According to the standard test method, ASTM C 365/C365M-11[38], stabilized honeycomb core with two facesheets bonded to both sides should be used to evaluate the flatwise compressive properties of the honeycomb cores, and the minimum cross-sectional area should be 2500 mm^2 for the honeycomb cores with 3.2 mm cell size. Since the stabilized honeycomb core with facesheets represents the nature of sandwich, honeycomb cores with facesheets bonded to both sides are usually tested in order to prevent possible local crushing. Different numerical models of the honeycomb core with facesheets were constructed in similar way by using the commercial finite element code, ABAQUS/EXPLICIT [17].

3.1 Unit cell model-1

The first simulation method is to model unit cell-1 as shown in Fig.2 of the whole honeycomb core by using two-dimensional shell elements. The unit cell-1 is $1/563$ times of the 2500 mm^2 honeycomb core in area. The meshes and boundary conditions of the unit cell model-1 were shown in Fig. 3. Two analytical rigid surfaces, Rigid_surf1 and Rigid_surf2, were used to represent the facesheets. The “Y” shape unit cell of the honeycomb core is explicitly modeled as hourglass-controlled reduced shell elements, S4R. The lengths of all the three cell walls are 0.925 mm, which is half of the cell wall length of the real honeycomb core. And the three cell walls are all 20 mm high. Angles between the three cell walls are all 120° . There are totally 1620 shell elements are used to represent the three cell walls, and the number of nodes is 1774.

The rigid surface, Rigid_surf2, was set to be fixed and the other rigid surface, Rigid_surf1, was set to move downward to simulate the displacement-controlled loading from the material testing machine. The three outer vertical edges of the three cell walls were applied X-Z plane symmetric constraints in the local coordinate systems, CSYS-1, CSYS-2 and CSYS-3, respectively. “Tie” constraints between the two rigid surfaces and the honeycomb core were used to simulate the glue conditions between honeycomb core and the two facesheets. Self-contact algorithm was used to define the possible contact among the cell walls to prevent the interpenetration between the folds in the honeycomb walls during folding process of the compression. The penalty and “hard” methods were used to define the tangential behaviors and normal behaviors of the possibly self-contact and the friction coefficient between the honeycomb cell walls was set to be 0.4 according to literature [18-19].

Aramid paper was modelled as an elasto-perfectly plastic material, and its compressive strength is

assumed to be the same as its tensile counterpart. Phenolic resin is a brittle material, whose strengths in tension and compression were taken as 60 MPa and 180 MPa, respectively. The phenolic resin was modelled as an elastic-brittle material and, in this model, the strength of the resin decreases from 180 MPa to a quite small value of 10 MPa after the compressive stress exceeds 180 MPa [16].

It is time intensive as the loading rate (displacement rate) in the explicit modelling is set to the same as that in testing (0.2 mm/min). Through trial studies, it was found that the loading (or displacement) rate of 1 mm/s or less would have a limited dynamic effect on the calculation results in this case.

3.2 Unit cell model-2

The second method is to model unit cell-1 by using three-dimensional solid elements representing the cell walls. The meshes and boundary conditions of the unit cell model-2 are shown in Fig.4. There are four layers of elements on the single cell walls (Cell wall-2 and Cell wall-3 in Fig. 5 (c)) in the thickness direction. The two outer layers of elements represent the resin layers. The two inner layers of elements represent the paper. There are seven layers of elements on the double cell wall (Cell wall-1 in Fig. 5 (c)) in the thickness direction. The two outmost layers of elements represent the resin layer, and their thickness is 0.008 mm. The four inner layers of elements represent the paper. The zero thickness cohesive elements in the middle represent the glue layer, which is shown in Fig. 5 (e). This matches with the real structure of the cell wall except in the cross corner region. The element size of the resin layers is 0.0925 mm x 0.0925mm x 0.008 mm, that of paper layers are 0.0925 mm x 0.0925mm x 0.025 mm, and that of the glue layer are 0.0925 mm x 0.0925mm x 0 mm.

Both the paper and resin layers are modelled as linear hexahedral elements of type C3D8R and the glue between the two paper. There are totally 30280 linear hexahedral elements of type C3D8R and 4422 8-node three-dimensional cohesive elements of type COH3D8 are used to represent the three cell walls, and the number of nodes are 41801. The adhesive is assumed to be isotropic and its strength and modulus are set to be 70 MPa and 5000 MPa, respectively.

The boundary conditions, contact relationships, constitute models and failure criteria and the calculation setup of this unit cell model are all the same with that of the whole-scale model described in Section 3.1.

Fig.4 Finite element model of honeycomb sandwich crushing

A bilinear traction-separation law was used in this study to govern the surface traction-separation relationship of the adhesive between the two paper layers. The quadratic nominal stress criterion was used to predict the damage initiation, which is shown in Eq. (1).

$$\left(\frac{\langle \sigma_n \rangle}{N_{max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_s}{S_{max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{T_{max}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

where, $\langle \sigma_n \rangle = \begin{cases} \sigma_n & \text{for } \sigma_n > 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } \sigma_n \leq 0 \end{cases}$, and the σ_n indicates the nominal stress in the pure normal mode, σ_s indicates nominal stress in the first shear direction, σ_t indicates nominal stress in the second shear direction.

3.3 Unit cell model-3

The third method is to model unit cell-2 shown in Fig.2 by using two-dimensional shell elements

representing the cell walls. The unit cell-2 is 1/281 times of the 2500 mm² honeycomb core in area. The meshes and boundary conditions of the unit cell model-3 were shown in Fig. 6. Two analytical rigid surfaces, Rigid_surf1 and Rigid_surf2, in an area of 5 mm x 5 mm represent the facesheets. The unit cell of the honeycomb core is explicitly modeled as hourglass-controlled reduced shell elements, S4R. The lengths of all the Cell wall-1, -2, -3, -4 are 0.925 mm, and that of the Cell wall-5 is 1.85 mm. Angles between the connected cell walls are all 120°. The meshes are sized to be 0.185 mm x 0.185 mm. Thus, there are totally 3240 elements and 3379 nodes.

Fig. 5 Finite element model of honeycomb sandwich crushing

The geometry and properties of the cell walls, the contact relationships, boundary conditions, constitute models and failure criteria, and the calculation step setup of this unit cell model are all the same with that of the whole-scale model described in Section 3.1.

3.4 Unit cell model-4

The fourth method is to model unit cell-3 by using two-dimensional shell elements representing the cell walls. The unit cell-2 is 1/93.7 times of the 2500 mm² honeycomb core in area. The meshes and boundary conditions of the unit cell model of the honeycomb sandwich structure under flatwise compressive loading were shown in Fig. 7. Two analytical rigid surfaces, Rigid_surf1 and Rigid_surf2, in an area of 8 mm x 8 mm represent the facesheets. The unit cell of the honeycomb core is explicitly modelled as hourglass-controlled reduced shell elements, S4R. The lengths of Cell wall-1~6 are 0.925 mm, and that of Cell wall-7~12 are 1.85 mm. Angles between the connected cell walls are all 120°. The meshes are sized to be 0.185 mm x 0.185 mm. Thus, there are totally 9720 elements and 9810 nodes.

The geometry and properties of the cell walls, the contact relationships, boundary conditions, constitute models and failure criteria, and the calculation step setup of this unit cell model are all the same with that of the whole-scale model described in Section 3.1.

Fig. 6 Finite element model of honeycomb sandwich crushing

4.4 Full-scale model

The full-scale model includes the whole area of the honeycomb core shown in Fig. 1, and the size of whole model is 1.04 times of the 2500 mm² honeycomb core in area. The meshes and boundary conditions of the whole-scale model of the honeycomb sandwich structure under flatwise compressive loading were shown in Figs. 3(a) and (b) illustrate the front and ISO views of the honeycomb core, respectively. The facesheets of the honeycomb sandwich are represented as two analytical rigid surfaces in an area of 60 mm x 60 mm. One reference point is located at the corner of each rigid surface. The honeycomb core with a height of 20 mm and an area of 50.8 mm x 51.2 mm is explicitly modelled as hourglass-controlled reduced shell elements, S4R. After conducting convergent analysis, the meshes are sized to be 0.185 mm x 0.185 mm, which means there are 10 elements on each edge of the honeycomb core. Thus, there are totally 977400 elements and 956148 nodes. Both the single and double cell walls were modelled as resin-paper-resin layered structures by using the “Composite Layup” function of Abaqus/CAE, and the thickness of the single and double walls of the honeycomb is set to be 0.07 mm and 0.124 mm, respectively.

The motions of the two rigid surfaces were governed by the motions of the two reference points, RP-1 and RP-2, respectively. The RP-2 was fixed in all 6 DOFs (U_x , U_y , U_z , R_x , R_y and R_z) and the RP-1 was fixed in two translational directions (U_x and U_y) and all three rotational directions (R_x , R_y and R_z), while a minus 15 mm compressive displacement load was applied to the RP-1 in U_z direction.

Fig.7 Finite element model of honeycomb sandwich crushing

4 VALIDATION

Flatwise compressive tests of five stabilized honeycomb cores with 2500 mm² cross-sectional area and 20 mm height were conducted in accordance with the ASTM C 365[20], as shown in Fig. 8. The detail test method and the result analysis were described in detail in Ref [16]. The compressive collapse load is tested to be 4300 N with corresponding displacement of 0.43 mm.

Fig. 8 Honeycomb core flatwise compressive test setup

The comparison of the load-displacement relationships between the simulation results and the test results is shown in Fig. 9. Generally, the finite element models give reasonable agreement with the experimental crushing response.

Fig. 9 Load-displacement curves of honeycomb core sandwich subject to flatwise compression

5 DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Effectiveness

Table 2 illustrates the calculate results and computing time of each models. From which, it can be seen the calculation of the whole-scale model is very time-consuming and the three unit cell models with two-dimensional shell elements representing the cell walls (Unit cell model-1, -3 and -4) are much more efficient with giving reasonable collapse loads. In addition, the calculation time of the unit cell model with three dimensional solid elements (Unit cell model-2) representing the cell walls is even longer than the whole-scale model with shell elements though the elements and nodes of the former are less.

Table 2 Effectiveness and efficiency of different models

	No. elements	No. nodes	Collapse load (N)	Error (%)	Computing time
Unit cell model-1	1620	1744	4386	2%	38'' minutes
Unit cell model-2	30280	39801	4388	2%	194 hours
Unit cell model-3	3240	3379	4360	1%	57 minutes
Unit cell model-4	9720	9810	4560	6%	2 hours
Whole-scale model	977400	956148	4482	4%	150 hours

5.2 Advantages of each modelling method

1) Unit cell model with shell elements

The computing efficiencies of the unit cell models with shell elements are high. They can be used to obtain the in-plane stress state of the resin layer and aramid layer, respectively. And furthermore, it can be used to judge the failure mechanism of the honeycomb core and to investigate the influence of the geometry and material parameters of the honeycomb and the imperfection of the honeycomb on the mechanical behaviours of the honeycomb core. For example, the in-plane stress state of the aramid paper and phenolic resin is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 In-plane stress state of the aramid paper and phenolic resin

2) Unit cell model with solid and cohesive elements

The unit cell model with solid elements representing the cell walls can predict the failure process more realistically than the unit models with shell elements. It can be used to predict the out-of-plane

stress of the cell walls, which is beneficial to judge whether resin will separate from the aramid paper and whether the double thickness cell walls will separate during loading. It can also be used to simulate the mechanical behaviour of the Nomex honeycomb core with initial imperfection [21].

3) Full-scale model

Whole-scale model can be used to predict overall failure mode of the honeycomb core. Furthermore, the whole scale model not only can be used on the crushing behaviour of the Nomex honeycomb core, also can be used on more general loading cases of the honeycomb core, such as impact loading with different angles and bending. The test results and simulation results of the Nomex honeycomb sandwich structure subjected to impacting are shown in Fig. 11. The penetration tests were conducted in accordance with the standard of American Society for Testing and Materials, ASTM D3763-02 [22] on an Instron Ceast 9350 Drop-weight testing machine.

Fig. 11 Comparison of the failure and deformation Nomex honeycomb sandwich structure subjected to impacting loading

6 CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The unit cell models with shell elements are very effective on solving crushing problem of the Nomex honeycomb cores.
- 2) The calculations of whole-scale model and the unit cell model with solid elements are both very time consuming.
- 3) The whole-scale model can be used to in crushing process and more general loading cases, such as impacting.
- 4) The unit cell model with solid elements and cohesive elements can be used investigate the debonding fracture of the double cell walls and the influence of bonding quality on the mechanical behaviour of the honeycomb core.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the DuPont Company for providing necessary technical data, and the authors would also like to appreciate the use of the cluster computers at School of Engineering in University of Liverpool for carrying out the calculation work in this study. The project is supported by CAST Innovation Foundation (14GFZ-JJ04-069) and Shanghai Municipal Natural Science Foundation (14ZR1422500).

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